

Post-print

Note: This is the author's accepted manuscript (AAM). The final published version of this article is available at the publisher's website:

<https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2025.2470780>

Understanding of Everyday Occupations through Agnes Heller's Theory of Everyday Life

Cleber Tiago Cirineu

<http://orcid.org/0000-0002-8986-9030>

Departamento de Terapia Ocupacional y Ciencia de la Ocupación, Facultad de Medicina, Universidad de Chile

Rodolfo Morrison

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2834-1646>

Escuela de Terapia Ocupacional, Facultad de Salud, Universidad Santo Tomás, Los Ángeles, Chile

Departamento de Terapia Ocupacional y Ciencia de la Ocupación, Facultad de Medicina, Universidad de Chile

Abstract: In parts of South America, the concept of *cotidiano* (everyday life) has been integrated into the knowledge production in Occupational Therapy, aiming to break with positivist and biomedical logic, thus facilitating the emergence of new methodological, theoretical, and practical proposals for the profession. In this context, this essay aims to establish a dialogue between Occupational Therapy, Occupational Science, and Agnes Heller's Theory of Everyday Life to identify possible contributions to the understanding of everyday occupations. Heller's theory provides fundamental conceptual elements such as heterogeneity, hierarchy, spontaneity, analogy, pragmatism, probability, economism, overgeneralization, precedents, provisional judgments, imitation, and intonation, which allow us to understand everyday life as a social and potentially transformative field. These interconnected elements can be key to analyzing everyday occupations, which constitute recurrent and essential practices within daily life, and they are examined as a more specific subtype of occupations. Finally, this article concludes with a section on the potential contributions of employing the theory of everyday life to understand everyday occupations, which could benefit both Occupational Therapy and Occupational Science.

Keywords: Theoretical perspectives; Occupational Therapy; Occupational Science; Everyday life; Everyday Occupations.

1. Introduction

Critical perspectives in Occupational Science (Farias et al., 2016; Galvaan, 2021; Morrison et al., 2021; Parkin & Johnson; Rudman, 2013, 2014; Simaan, 2020) and in Occupational Therapy (Galheigo, 2020; Galvaan et al., 2022; Guajardo & Malfitano, 2023; Hammell, 2011; Lapierre & Samacá, 2024; Monclus & Tarrès, 2016; Taff & Putnam, 2022; Turcotte & Holmes, 2021) have challenged the individualistic and hegemonic logics that have developed since the inception of both disciplines. In this journey, alliances have been proposed to reflect from other perspectives—beyond the global North—on other concepts and theories, even beyond the concept of occupation (Malfitano, 2022). This has led to efforts to foster dialogue between different disciplines, such as Social Occupational Therapy and Critical Occupational Science (Junior et al., 2024; Leite, 2024). In these discussions, terms such as *cotidiano* have become interesting debate points.

Thus, in parts of South America, the concept of *cotidiano* has been incorporated into the knowledge production of occupational therapy to enrich perspectives on the understanding and intervention processes of the profession (Albornoz et al., 2023; Bezerra et al., 2022; Cazeiro et al., 2022; Galheigo, 2020; Salles & Matsukura, 2013, 2015). This concept seeks to contribute theoretical support in response to the emergence of new methodological, theoretical, and practical proposals for occupational therapy (Galheigo, 2020; Salles & Matsukura, 2013, 2015). For instance, in Brazil, since the mid-1990s, the concept of *cotidiano* has been a key axis in emancipatory practices across various professional fields, particularly in occupational therapy, promoting self-care, sociability, collective organization, and social participation. Academic production has gone beyond theoretical advocacy, describing concrete practices that address the realities of individuals and groups facing disability, suffering, and discrimination. Since 2010, the concept of *cotidiano* has gained relevance, especially in its use as a theoretical and practical framework within occupational therapy, fostering a conceptual debate regarding its terminology and its relationship with other terms such as activity, occupation, and praxis (Galheigo, 2020; Bezerra et al., 2022; Salles & Matsukura, 2013). These conceptual studies are fundamental for the theoretical development of the discipline, emphasizing that the meanings of these terms acquire different

dimensions in academic and professional contexts (Cazeiro et al., 2022; Galvaan, 2021; Maximino & Tedesco, 2016).

In the field of occupational science, there are still few approaches that integrate this concept to study occupations (Gonçalves & Malfitano, 2020). In both disciplines, it could be a contribution to the study and understanding of the occupations that people perform daily.

The *cotidiano* has been understood from different theoretical approaches, one of them being Agnes Heller's Theory of the Everyday Life (Heller, 2008). Her theory offers a critical and reflective approach to the conditions through which humans construct our history, from previously given conditions, aspiring to certain ends limited by this same construction process but with possibilities of making changes. Heller (2008) addresses overcoming alienation in everyday life by using Goethe's concept of "life conduct" to propose the humanization of daily life. Instead of eliminating the spontaneous structure of everyday life, Heller emphasizes the need to reestablish a conscious relationship between the individual and society. In this way, she advocates for creating new ways of organizing life based on an ethical and active relationship, transforming everyday life into a moral and political action.

Heller's theory provides important conceptual elements for understanding everyday life, such as heterogeneity, hierarchy, spontaneity, analogy, among others. All these elements are interconnected and essential for everyday life. Heller (2008) warns that this understanding should not be fragmented, as doing so would limit the comprehensive understanding of the individual. Furthermore, it is necessary to be cautious about the crystallization of the concepts described above to avoid falling into alienation, understanding that everyday life is a field conducive to alienation when the individual lives a life restricted by rules and routines, characterized by conformism, where they unconsciously assume the roles imposed by society.

Our proposal aims to reflect on everyday life as a space containing the occupations that occur daily. These are the everyday occupations that occur within everyday life (an idea we will develop later). Thus, it is possible to apply Heller's theory to study everyday occupations.

Occupation is a widely discussed concept in occupational therapy and occupational science, with multiple perspectives, theories, and conceptual frameworks proposed for its understanding (Junior et al., 2024). Particularly, we will take the concept of everyday occupations because it dialogues more closely with the anthropology of everyday life (Hasselkus, 2006), where Heller's proposal can be established. It is important to note that our aim is not to propose a single form of analysis of these occupations. We seek to establish a proposal for analyzing occupations immersed in everyday life. Understanding everyday life as one of the multiple spheres of reality¹ while highlighting it as the one that is at the center of historical events (Heller, 2008).

We believe this reflection could contribute to occupational therapy and occupational science, providing a perspective that strengthens the deepening of the study of occupation. Thus, the question guiding this essay is: What could be the contribution of Heller's theory of everyday life to studying everyday occupations in occupational therapy and occupational science? How could this analysis contribute to both disciplines?

First, we provide an overview of Agnes Heller's Theory of Everyday Life to address these questions. Subsequently, we review how Heller's concept of the everyday has been understood in occupational therapy and occupational science. We then propose a conceptualization of everyday occupations drawing from Betty R. Hasselkus's framework (2006), followed by a potential analysis of everyday occupations through Agnes Heller's theory of the everyday. Finally, we conclude with a section on the potential contributions of employing the theory of the everyday life in understanding everyday occupations, which could benefit both occupational therapy and occupational science.

2. The Theory of Everyday Life by Heller

¹ It is important to understand that Heller proposes everyday life as one expression of reality, not the only one. In this sense, she presents life as heterogeneous, where political structures, science, art, morality, production, among others, intersect (Heller, 2008).

Agnes Heller's analysis of everyday life is based on the capitalist framework, where social interactions and individual practices reflect the structures of power and predominant economic relationships (Heller, 2008). Heller draws upon Marx, who identifies everyday life as a sphere where capitalist relations of production generate alienation, affecting all dimensions of human existence (Marx, 1844). This alienation manifests in the pursuit of meeting basic needs and cultural aspirations shaped by consumption and production dynamics (Heller, 2008).

In her work "The Theory of Need in Marx" (1978), Agnes Heller delves into the Marxist theory of human needs, emphasizing how these needs are intrinsically linked to capitalism's economic and social structures. Central to her analysis is the notion that individual needs are not mere expressions of personal desires but are mediated by production relations imposed by the capitalist system. Thus, everyday life becomes the terrain where these relations are reproduced and where individuals directly experience the contradictions and alienations of the dominant mode of production.

Marx (1844), in his critique of capitalism, identifies alienation as a pervasive phenomenon that affects not only the worker in their direct relationship with the productive process but permeates all spheres of everyday life. Heller (2008) expands on this critique by highlighting how alienation manifests in individuals' daily activities, where capitalist dynamics of consumption and production shape the pursuit of meeting basic needs and cultural aspirations. Thus, everyday life not only reflects structures of power and economic domination but also reproduces and reinforces the social inequalities inherent in capitalism.

Thus, Heller argues that "history is the substance of society" (2008, p. 12), where the human being, possessing social objectivity, is responsible for constructing and transmitting any social structure. Since everyday life is also the individual's life, it is both particular and generic, as humans are always in relation to other human beings (Heller, 2008).

For Heller, objectification involves the appropriation of tools and products (everything available to humans in the social environment), customs (everything relevant to social

coexistence), and language (enabling communication and serving as a means of survival) (Guimarães, 2002). Because humans are born into everyday life, they "assume as given the functions of everyday life and exercise them in parallel" (Heller, 2008, p. 38), as there exists a reality of building a relationship both with their social environment and their own lived experience.

For Heller, each individual possesses individual and generic characteristics that can be conscious or unconscious. In this sense, "the relatively free (autonomous) choice of generic and particular elements is common to all individuality; but, in this formulation, the term relatively must be emphasized" (Heller, 2008, p. 37).

Thus, Heller argues that everyday life develops through social relationships among people, articulated between social production and reproduction, the public and the private. It is important to remember that humans can only reproduce when they assume a function in the social context through objectifications that "involve an action of humans on the object, transforming it for their use and benefit" (Heller, 2008, p. 12).

Therefore, everyday life is constituted by elements that encompass regularity, uniformity, and repetition, allowing the ordering of life and adopting characteristics that serve as models among living beings. When transformations occur in these models, there will be transformations in everyday life. Through these transformations, rules, and norms are established and internalized through the learning process so that humans build mutual cooperation and assign meanings to their adaptation to the social environment (Heller, 2002).

In conclusion, Heller's proposal portrays everyday life as a field of struggle and social reproduction under capitalism, offering spaces for criticism and transformation towards more just and equitable forms of human organization.

3. Everyday Life (*cotidiano*) in Occupational Therapy and Occupational Science

Malfitano et al. (2023) provide an important reflection on the use of terms and concepts in occupational therapy, highlighting that the concept of occupation alone is limited in accounting for all possible approaches within the profession. They reflect on how concepts are historically constructed in particular situated contexts, considering the culture, politics, and interests in which they are formed. Additionally, they emphasize that in the field of occupational therapy, concepts often originate from the Global North, making it necessary to question their applicability in local contexts.

Regarding the concept of *cotidiano*, they point out that there is no literal translation into English, and the most commonly used approximation is "everyday life." However, this translation does not encompass the sociopolitical dimensions of life. They attribute the extension of the concept of *cotidiano*, particularly in the Brazilian context, to the "emergence of critical thinking about the social functions of the professional" (p. 126). Thus, they refer to how it is constituted as a way to critique practices focused solely on the individual, specifically challenging the instrumental and technical perspective of life (Malfitano et al., 2023).

Similarly, Galheigo (2020) notes that in part of the Brazilian context, the concept of *cotidiano* began to gain visibility from 1988 onwards, highlighting Berenice Rosa Francisco, who critiques the understanding of the use of Activities of Daily Living (ADLs) in the profession. Francisco argues that *cotidiano* should be understood as a social and historical construction associated with a human practice that can be rethought and redefined. Thus, the concept of *cotidiano* gains prominence, being understood as a socio-historical construct for understanding individuals and collectives. Since the 1990s, it has become a basis for some occupational Therapy practices to support and sustain research and interventions (Cruz et al., 2021).

Leão and Salles (2016) emphasize that the concept of *cotidiano* can influence the direction of territorial practice proposals and facilitate the achievement of intervention goals. Among them, each person's social inclusion, autonomy, and subjectivity are factors that come from teamwork and are intrinsic to psychosocial rehabilitation. According to these authors, it is through the articulation between the "micro" and "macro" vision of *cotidiano* that

psychosocial rehabilitation can be carried out, allowing the social inclusion of individuals in the territorial sphere². Thus, a "micro" vision of *cotidiano* considers the individual's particularities, considering it important to lead their own life, to be able to make their own choices and to have rights as a citizen. However, an interface between the particular and the collective is also important, allowing people, from a "macro" vision of *cotidiano*, to construct and rethink their lives in society. This construction can be influenced and interfered with by ways of life through public policies, the health system, and the social system, forms of production, and even how society establishes ideologies (Maximino & Tedesco, 2016).

Similarly, Abumusse (2016) points out that *cotidiano* arises from the composition of day-to-day activities related to work organization and participation, private life, leisure, and rest, all based on social ties and links in a specific context and historical moment. For Maximino and Tedesco (Maximino & Tedesco, 2016), all participation and co-participation, at a micro or macro level, have a political bias when they allow changes and transformations in individuals and society.

Marcolino (Marcolino, 2016) emphasizes the importance of understanding each person's life history, comprehending the implications, repercussions, and even disruptions that affect their *cotidiano* (everyday life). Along these lines, Salles and Matsukura (Salles & Matsukura, 2015) state that disruptions reflect significant transformations in individuals' everyday lives, with difficulties in performing occupations they once engaged in smoothly, resulting in identity ruptures.

Finally, Galheigo (2020) points out that studies on *cotidiano* focus on how human beings live, encompassing space, time, culture, life histories, and social relationships, accessing each person's experiences, knowledge, and representations. This perspective is broader than just focusing on Activities of Daily Living.

² The social space that we can call territory is a relational reality, composed, on one hand, by natural and geographical objects, and on the other, by society in motion. The dynamic aspect corresponds to the interrelations established between individuals, mediated by cultural, social, legislative, political, economic, and social aspects, producing transformations, which occur through the natural landscape and the social history inscribed and reflected in lifestyles and in what is perceived and understood about the place" (Santos, 2007, cited by Leão and Barros, 2012, p. 576).

In the field of occupational science, we could not identify writings that captured Heller's perspective for understanding occupation, except for an article by Gonçalves & Malfitano (2020). In this research, it is noted that:

There is no word perfectly corresponding to *cotidiano* in the English lexicon. The terms "everyday", "everyday life", or "daily life" are not direct translations and have other meanings, but in studies aimed at conceptualizing *cotidiano* it has been translated as everyday life (pp. 311-312).

In their study, the authors use the concept of *cotidiano* in dialogue with the concept of occupation, indicating that this construct inherently encompasses political, social, and economic aspects within its understanding (Gonçalves & Malfitano, 2020). The absence of writings on Heller in the field of occupational science reinforces our idea of delving into this theory to contribute to potential uses.

4. Rethinking Occupation

The ways of understanding occupation have gone through different theoretical currents and epistemological perspectives. In the last decade, transactionalism has opened the understanding of occupation, enabling occupational science to consider other ways of framing the place that occupation takes in human beings. Mainly, the contributions of pragmatism, in the voice of John Dewey, have been crucial in proposing how it is possible to understand occupation as an inherent part of the person where it is expressed in a "transaction" with the environment, but not from the split understanding of the person with the environment, but rather understanding functional coordination that does not allow for separation (Cutchin & Dickie, 2013).

Thus, different authors (Aldrich, 2008; Cutchin & Dickie, 2012; Fritz & Cutchin, 2017; Kuo, 2018; Lavalley, 2017) have proposed that the transactional perspective brings new

perspectives to the way of studying occupation, as it establishes it as a part of the person and not as something separate from them, which complicates the ways of understanding it.

In a similar line, other authors in South America have pointed out that there is no occupation separate from the person, as occupation is the person themselves, understanding both constructs as a totality (Cerón & Morrison, 2019, 2024; Guajardo, 2012; Morrison et al., 2016; Schliebener, 2018; Yañez & Pizarro, 2015). The person is and expresses themselves through occupation, so our nature would be occupational, and we would always be in occupations (Morrison & Poblete-Almendras, 2023).

Some authors have questioned how certain truths about occupation have been established. Using Wilcock's Theory of the Occupational Nature of Human Beings, they point out that occupation would be established as an attribute rather than a "nature" (Schliebener, 2015; Yañez & Pizarro, 2015). However, Schliebener adopts this premise to contemplate "the occupational" as a manner of engaging with the world. (Schliebener, 2021), as that which defines that human beings are what they are and that allows their expression (Schliebener, 2020) and establishes that the world's things exist insofar as the being occupies itself (Schliebener, 2018). That is, since the human being is an occupational being, it constitutes a way of relating interdependently in a network of permanent and continuous occupations that aim for significance and their own existence in the world. Schliebener (2018) refers to this issue in the following quote:

We can conclude that occupation, finally, is ourselves in a strict sense. Understanding the human being as occupation is to understand the human being as human, inseparably from their world. Thus, notions of man and occupation as two separate elements would be set aside, which sometimes meet and sometimes do not (p. 259)³.

³ Own translation from Spanish. Original text in Spanish: "Podemos concluir que la ocupación, finalmente, somos nosotros mismos en estricto sentido. Comprender al ser humano en cuánto ocupación, es entender al ser humano en cuanto humano, inseparablemente de su mundo. Así, se dejarían de lado aquellas nociones de hombre y de ocupación, como dos elementos separados, que a veces se encuentran y otras no (Schliebener, 2018, p. 259).

That way, occupation "appears" in doing, as it is the human being who exists through occupation, or as Gutiérrez (2011) proposes, as part of the constitutive processes of "becoming" oneself. Thus, occupation is that expression of "the human" that constructs "the human." Establishing a permanent transactional recursivity that permeates all our ways of being-doing in the world.

This understanding can also be accessed from the existential analytics of the German philosopher Martin Heidegger (Schliebener, 2020). He suggests that it is in occupation where one can obtain "[...] the most immediate and proper ontological characteristics of the world with which we deal" (Heidegger, 2008, p. 31).

For Heidegger, it is necessary to mention that the living is found in the context of experience expressively, that is, insofar as "[...] life in general and everywhere is only expression and is lived in expression" (Heidegger, 2014) (p. 162).

From this perspective, it is highlighted that it is not possible to separate occupation from human beings or each of them from the world, as they belong to the same phenomenon, to a totality. Thus, the human being expresses *occupationally* in the world that he himself signifies in the context of possible relative life projects. These moments of experience are what give life to that which is in its context, that is, in *situation*. In other words, it is concluded that *understanding occupation vitalizes* and gives life. In this way, a perspective that incorporates such comprehensive movements considers occupation-human-being-environment as a unitary, inseparable phenomenon. And therefore, it develops an integral approach with others (Schliebener, 2020).

4.1. Hasselkus' everyday occupations

Hasselkus points out that everyday occupations are ways of organizing the world we live in and ways of making sense of our lives. They are often "seen but unnoticed" (Hasselkus, 2006, p. 626) and are rooted in the context of everyday life. Everyday occupations are part of the

rhythms of everyday life; they are the occupational fabric of our everyday life experiential worlds (Hasselkus, 2006) and construct our humanity.

Everyday life is also a paradox in our lives. The small behaviors that make up the realm of each of our everyday lives are more than what we have in common with others; they also represent our exquisite individuality and distinction (Hasselkus, 2006).

Hasselkus (2006) points out that one of the reasons why everyday occupation is often seen but overlooked is because we employ categories. Thus, everyday occupations are perceived from a common denominator: the anonymity of everyday life. What often goes unnoticed are the complexities and singularities of the everyday life.

Other reasons relate to the low social importance attributed to "the everyday." Being synonymous with mundane and trivial, where the ordinary is devalued. Thus, social and economic structural invisibility occurs that relegates daily activities to the private and personal sphere, minimizing their public visibility and recognition as significant contributions to society (Giddens & Sutton, 2021).

In addition to the above, there is a hierarchy of values where exceptional, innovative, and spectacular aspects are privileged over the regular and constant (Bauman, 2013). This leads to an uneven valuation of everyday activities compared to events or actions that capture media or cultural attention. Furthermore, ideals of consumption and market dominate public life; everyday activities that do not contribute, from a capitalist and patriarchal perspective to economic growth or consumption, may be underestimated or undervalued (Miller, 2008).

4.2. Complexifying everyday occupations

Taking primarily the proposals of Hasselkus and Schliebener into account, we consider that the process described above occurs on a daily basis. We consider that *human beings are occupational beings in everyday life through everyday occupations*. Thus, we understand everyday occupations as necessary for the expression of humanity to the extent that human beings engage and construct their everyday life. Not as actions external to what is possible as a human being, but rather as *being* in everyday life. Everyday occupations would construct the everyday life and the very existence of human beings, as they are a recursive expression of human existence.

All human beings are immersed in everyday life. We are born into it. Our intellectual abilities, senses, manipulative skills, feelings, passions, ideologies, and our social position, among other aspects, constitute our humanity and are expressed through everyday life (Heller, 2008). However, never in its entirety. We do not have time for that. Therefore, we believe that we express the partiality of our heterogeneous existence, at various moments, through everyday occupations, permanently, concatenated, and without a greater teleology than the one humanity itself has constructed as such.

We consider that socialization and historical construction processes would depend on the everyday occupations that shape and reproduce everyday life. In this framework, where everyday occupation constructs everyday life, and everyday life constructs everyday occupation, everyday occupations express the existence of human beings as ontologically occupational beings.

Thus, everyday occupations would be invested with a sense of purpose, meaning, and the culture of those who perform them in relation to contexts such as the economic, the social, etc. (Morrison et al., 2011). They express actions within a transactional relationship in everyday life, which are expressed in a myriad of occupations (Christiansen & Townsend, 2009) and constitute the humanity of individuals (Schliebener, 2020).

Thereby, we understand everyday occupations as a specific subgroup within human occupations, those that occur within the framework of daily life and are deeply rooted in

social, historical, and cultural contexts. These occupations are characterized by their regularity, uniformity, and repetition, integrating into routines that enable the organization of life (Heller, 2002; Maximino & Tedesco, 2016). They are essential practices that respond not only to individual needs but also to social and economic demands mediated by the production relations of the capitalist system (Heller, 1978; Galheigo, 2020).

In this sense, daily life, as the space where everyday occupations unfold, is configured as the terrain where the structures of the dominant mode of production are reproduced. Here, people experience the inherent contradictions of these dynamics, as individual needs are not mere expressions of personal desires but are deeply influenced by the demands of capitalist consumption and production (Bezerra et al., 2022; Heller, 2008). These dynamics shape how individuals seek to fulfill both their basic needs and cultural aspirations, highlighting the tensions between autonomy and alienation (Rudman, 2013; Galvaan, 2021).

From this perspective, the repetitiveness of everyday occupations not only reflects stability but also an adaptation to the social rules and norms that are learned and internalized over time (Heller, 2002; Salles & Matsukura, 2015). This learning process enables the construction of shared meanings and establishes models of mutual cooperation in daily life. However, when significant transformations occur in these models—whether through cultural, social, or economic changes—everyday occupations are also altered, demonstrating the individual's capacity to reinterpret and adapt to an ever-changing environment (Aldrich, 2008; Galheigo, 2020).

Although these occupations are part of the routine, they are not devoid of individual agency. Choices made within everyday occupations, though conditioned by the system, are relatively autonomous, reflecting a constant interaction between external impositions and the individual's subjectivity (Heller, 2008). This balance between structure and action, repetition and transformation, makes everyday occupations a dynamic and essential space for understanding the human experience.

On the other hand, these occupations differ from extraordinary events (though this does not mean they cannot drive profound transformations in the system).

This concept differs from "everyday life" in that while everyday life is the space in which various human actions occur, "everyday occupation" specifically refers to the activities that people perform recurrently within that space. In other words, everyday occupations are the constitutive elements of everyday life.

This distinction becomes relevant within Agnes Heller's theory of everyday life, where she conceptualizes everyday life not just as a space of repetition but as a space for social transformation and critique. In this sense, "everyday occupation" and "everyday life" are intrinsically interrelated, but everyday occupations specifically refer to the activities that enable the construction and reproduction of social and personal life within their daily context.

Moreover, extraordinary events involve developing non-everyday occupations or requiring their modification and adaptation. These events disrupt or alter the usual routine and include crisis situations such as natural disasters, armed conflicts, critical moments in people's lives, migration processes, or severe illnesses that require immediate adaptation or response, among others.

Thus, occupational scientists have investigated people who engage in occupations outside their everyday lives. Some examples of these studies include individuals who manage to construct their occupations during migration processes (Arola et al., 2018; Farias & Asaba, 2013) or forced migration (Adrian, 2013; Raanaas et al., 2019; Suleman & Whiteford, 2013); during the COVID-19 pandemic (Junior et al., 2024; Krishnagiri & Adler, 2022; Salar et al., 2022); in natural disaster situations (Sima et al., 2017); or those related to concepts such as occupational disruption (Nizzero et al., 2017); and occupational transition (Domínguez et al., 2018; Morrison et al., 2023); among others. Several of these studies examined how everyday occupations are central to facing the adversity of extraordinary events affecting these individuals' everyday lives.

Simultaneously, occupational therapists have worked to help restore the everyday nature of occupations in the face of extraordinary events, such as armed conflicts (Duarte Cuervo, 2023), natural disasters (Parente et al., 2017); forced migration (Krishnakumaran et al. 2022); among others. Therefore, delving into the concept of everyday occupations is a relevant aspect of practice and research.

From occupational science, the relevance of everyday occupations has been studied to construct meaning for people across different contexts. For instance, Aguilar et al. (2010) explored how older adults' engagement with computers contributes to their sense of control, daily activity, and social interaction and is highly valued in their daily lives. Bundgaard (2005) investigated how meal preparations are central to constructing both collective and individual identity in everyday life. Similarly, Absolom & Roberts (2011) underscored the value of communal dining as an everyday occupation.

These are just a few examples of the numerous studies in occupational science that address the significance of everyday occupations. However, the previous examples have not engaged with critical perspectives to understand how everyday life serves as the space where everyday occupations can either transform or reproduce alienating situations for individuals.

Therefore, as a possible way to analyze the complexity of everyday occupations, we propose that Heller's theory could allow for a deeper exploration of the elements that compose the everyday and, therefore, the place where everyday occupations occur, being able to analyze everyday occupation itself from this recursive and indivisible relationship.

5. Applications of Heller's Theory of Everyday Life to the study of everyday occupations

The Theory of Everyday Life proposes that everyday life occurs in the productions and exchanges of the social sphere among individuals, emphasizing that this insertion of the individual constitutes a network of social relations in different everyday activities (Heller, 2008).

Through the historical process, individuals learn from the social environment and constitute themselves, considering what has been built in the past and aiming for possibilities in the future (Salles & Matsukura, 2013). Considering a long historical journey, each person gives meaning to history, leaving space for everyday life and placing it as the protagonist (Heller, 2008). Thus, for the author:

Everyday life is the life of every individual. Everyone lives in it, without exception, regardless of their position in the division of intellectual and physical labor [...]. Everyday life is the life of the whole individual; that is, individuals participate in everyday life with all aspects of their individuality, their personality. All his senses, all his intellectual abilities, his manipulative skills, his feelings, passions, ideas, and ideologies are set 'in motion' in him (Heller, 2008, p. 31).

By understanding that everyday life is also individual life, it is both particular and generic; that is, the human being is always in relation to other people (Heller, 2008), with a constant relationship with the social context at a given historical moment and situated in the same time and space. Generic activities, which we understand as everyday occupations, possess the generic aspects of human beings (although the objectives and motivations may be individual) (Heller, 2008).

For a possible way to analyze everyday occupations, we propose taking the twelve elements for understanding and analyzing Heller's Theory of Everyday Life.

Firstly, *heterogeneity*, which refers to the condition of human plurality, is simply manifested by the existence of the subject, but for its execution, various conditions must exist. Heterogeneity underscores the diversity of experiences and contexts that enrich everyday life, highlighting the inherent variety of the human condition. All occupations that people carry out with different degrees of importance, meanings, and contents are expressed within them (Heller, 2008). These develop over the course of individual history (Salles, 2011). Here, the sufficient existence of the person for the occurrence of occupations is noted despite adverse conditions for each one to be carried out.

The second element is *hierarchy*, which refers to the ability to establish priorities of action according to the meaning that the subject attributes to each activity and the degree of importance these activities hold for them. Thus, it involves setting priorities in occupations: when a particular occupation assumes a central and determining position in relation to others (Heller, 2008). For this element, it is important to emphasize the conditions of human plurality and awareness of personal interests, values, and preferences, as well as the awareness that each person has of the world, relating to (or determined by) the norms and rules imposed by the context.

Spontaneity is another element that relates to social behaviors linked to unplanned, improvised actions without considering future consequences (Guimarães, 2002), being a dominant characteristic as it appears in the forms of both private and public motivations (Heller, 2008). For this, the individual has freedom and autonomy. Thus, some everyday occupations can be carried out spontaneously without the need for prior planning. This element highlights the individual's ability to respond flexibly and creatively to changing circumstances in their environment, allowing for dynamic and spontaneous adaptation.

The *analogy* is understood from experiences already lived and/or known (Heller, 2008), that is, it is an experience that "manifests itself to maintain the repetition of the same procedure", without considering criticality in actions, with pre-established behaviors that can even be considered prejudiced (Guimarães, 2002, p.17), by taking advantage of an event that was successful in the past to determine successful action in the present in similar situations. Thus, certain everyday occupations may not necessarily be questioned by each individual, as they would be repetitions of permanent patterns over time.

Pragmatism is the element that arises from empirical thought with a tendency not to reflect and not to reproduce something that has not been successfully confirmed in practice, that is, there is no rationality, and it does not need a theory that closely justifies daily practice (Guimarães, 2002), relating to knowledge of the world through actions grounded in reality. That is, everyday occupations are performed without necessary confirmation, based on

science or another form of confirmation. Pragmatism allows for action grounded in reality, using knowledge of the world. This practical and realistic approach guides the individual's decisions and actions, ensuring they are aligned with the conditions and possibilities of the environment. Pragmatism emphasizes the utility and effectiveness of actions based on tangible reality.

Probability is related to the possibility that an action and empirical thought may succeed or fail; depending on the positive outcome, this may or may not be repeated (Guimarães, 2002). That is, it occurs when there is an objective relationship between one's occupations and their consequences (Heller, 2008), which is confirmed by previous experiences or lived experiences. This allows the individual to make informed and adaptive decisions.

Probability is also related to *economism*, which relates to not wasting time or effort, using the resources made available by society to facilitate their practical use (Guimarães, 2002). This element is closely related to routine, that is, occupations that can be performed automatically, more quickly, and efficiently by each individual. Routine is key in this process, allowing for smooth execution without constant conscious effort, thus optimizing the individual's time and energy.

Another element is *repetition*, which facilitates the execution of automatic actions that promote economism. Using environmental adaptation resources and routine, everyday occupations can be carried out efficiently without needing constant reflection. This simplifies daily tasks and contributes to operational efficiency in everyday life (Heller, 2008).

There is also the use of the concept of *overgeneralization* or *overgeneralizing judgments*, which is a characteristic of everyday life and is based on trust, these being "provisional judgments that practice confirms, or at least does not refute, to the extent that, based on them, we are able to act and orient ourselves" (Heller, 2008, p. 53). However, Guimarães (2002) states that overgeneralization or provisional judgments occur based on a belief that has already happened. It tends to repeat itself and help the individual classify their thoughts as correct or incorrect. It is also worth noting that provisional judgments can be classified into

two types: *overgeneralized judgments*, based on trust, and *prejudices*, based on faith (Heller, 2008), which Guimarães (2002) points out as those not supported by any theory, as they come from empirical thoughts of daily experiences and social life of individuals.

Using precedents is "more important for knowledge of the situation than for knowledge of people." It is a useful indicator for our behavior, for our attitude" (Heller, 2008, p. 55); this element interfaces with routine procedures, that is, an automatic and/or repetitive action that occurs based on an action that preceded others (Guimarães, 2002). Precedents provide indicators based on previous actions and generate the reproduction of those same actions, fostering routine, accommodation, and permanence. Previous experience and lived experience are essential for establishing these precedents and guiding future behavior.

Imitation or *mimesis* is the action that allows assimilating everything that happens in the environment, enabling the individual's relationship with the social environment (Heller, 2008). It involves the assimilation of social relationships through imitation. Under conditions of healthy development, the mere existence of the subject is sufficient for this process to occur, which is fundamental for socialization and learning of behaviors and social norms. Mimesis facilitates social integration and cohesion through observing and repeating behaviors (Guimarães, 2002). Therefore, these characteristics of everyday occupations can be linked throughout the lifespan.

Finally, intonation refers to the tone in which a person frames human relationships, validates the uniqueness and singularity of the human being, marks their differences, and configures themselves through communication (Heller, 2008). This element stands out for validating the authenticity of each person, with all their diversities, when performing everyday occupations.

Based on the above, we consider Salles (2011) and Guimarães (2002) who propose that all these elements are articulated with each other and are essential for everyday life, drawing attention to the crystallization of these elements, not to turn towards alienation. Unalienated or alienating everyday life is when a person can appropriate their reality and demarcate with their own personality the development of their life, taking into account the web of

relationships with the environment in which they live (Heller, 2008) and performing everyday occupations that allow them, for example, to assert their occupational rights (Durocher et al., 2014).

Deepening the understanding of alienation, Salles (2011) and Guimarães (2002) emphasize that this concept is understood here as a condition in which the individual lives a life restricted by norms and routines, characterized by a conformism in which roles imposed by society are assumed unconsciously. This phenomenon can be especially prevalent in everyday life, an area where practices and customs are reproduced automatically and without critical reflection.

In this regard, Heller (2008) argues that alienation in everyday life can hinder individuals' full and satisfactory development, as it limits the capacity for systematic reflection on their own living conditions within the social context. Everyday life, being composed of repetitive habits and routines, risks becoming a space where individuals act mechanically without questioning the structures and norms that govern their existence.

Alienation manifests as a separation between the individual and their capacity for critical agency, reducing them to mere executors of roles and tasks dictated by a social order that has not been questioned or transformed by their conscious action. This condition is particularly concerning, as it prevents individuals from recognizing and transforming the conditions of their own oppression and limitations.

For Salles (2011) and Guimarães (2002), studies and reflections on everyday life must include a constant critique of the ways in which norms and routines can become mechanisms of alienation. In this way, the possibility is opened for individuals to reclaim their capacity for agency and become active subjects in transforming their social reality. In agreement with this perspective, Heller highlights the importance of a critical consciousness that enables individuals to identify and overcome the forms of alienation present in their everyday life, thus promoting a more integral and authentic development.

This understanding of everyday life from the perspective of Agnes Heller for occupational therapy and occupational science highlights the depth of occupations since these occur in everyday life and how this allows human beings to be what they are (Schliebener, 2020), constituting all their singularities and diversities.

6. Final thoughts

The concept of "everyday occupation" proposed in this article aims to move beyond traditional notions of "occupations" and "everyday life" by focusing on the specific dynamics that shape activities within concrete sociocultural and political frameworks. Inspired by the work of Agnes Heller and aligned with critical perspectives within the discipline, this concept does not merely describe routine and repetition. Still, it emphasizes how everyday occupations can reflect, perpetuate, or challenge structures of power and inequality. Its originality lies in analyzing how these activities, shaped by historical and contextual dynamics, articulate meanings and values that sustain and give form to everyday life. This approach enriches the critical understanding of human occupations and underscores their sociopolitical relevance.

Also, we consider it a significant contribution to deepening the analysis of the concept of everyday occupations in occupational therapy and occupational science from Heller's perspective for several reasons.

Firstly, everyday occupations gain paramount importance in both disciplines by being situated within human experience and respecting diversity. They encompass various scenarios where individuals engage in their everyday activities, thereby valuing their unique significance and meaning and addressing their particular and collective needs.

This perspective challenges the occupational therapist's practice in the contemporary context characterized by capitalist principles. It prompts a critical examination of the boundaries and constraints of "professional work," which often confines itself solely to social and economic realities without adequately considering the intrinsic meanings and values embedded within

everyday activities. This aligns with critical perspectives such as Occupational Therapies from Global South (Simó et al., 2016), for example, Social Occupational Therapy (Lopes & Malfitano, 2016), which also challenge the contexts where their own practice occurs.

Moreover, everyday occupations serve as a central axis for understanding professional identity within both disciplines, occupational therapy and occupational science. By delving into the analysis of both simple and complex everyday activities in specific temporal and spatial contexts, it becomes possible to comprehend the intricate interplay between individuals and their surroundings. This approach facilitates the fulfillment of basic biological, social, and psychological needs at both individual and collective levels.

Furthermore, the clinical significance of everyday occupations cannot be overstated. They form the cornerstone of occupational therapy practice. Through a comprehensive analysis, occupational therapists gain insights into how these activities influence the health and well-being of individuals, thereby informing targeted interventions and treatments.

Contextualizing actions within the broader framework of everyday occupations allows occupational therapists to develop more effective, person-centered therapeutic strategies. In this way, action plans can be adjusted to address the needs and particularities of everyone, considering environmental, social, and cultural aspects.

Everyday occupations also play a crucial role in promoting social participation and community integration. By identifying barriers and facilitators to participation, occupational therapists can develop strategies to enhance meaningful engagement in everyday activities, fostering overall well-being and social inclusion.

In the case of occupational science, Heller's perspective emphasizes the sociopolitical and cultural dimensions of everyday life, allowing for a more comprehensive understanding of how occupations are situated within broader social contexts. This can help researchers explore how daily activities are influenced by and contribute to the social and political

environment, providing a richer and more nuanced analysis of participation in everyday occupations.

Additionally, it highlights the impact of sociopolitical factors on everyday occupations. Researchers can examine how systemic issues such as inequality, power dynamics, and cultural norms shape and constrain daily activities, leading to more socially responsible and justice-oriented occupational practices.

By understanding everyday life as a social construction, researchers can critique and move beyond approaches that focus solely on individual agency, thereby recognizing occupation's collective and relational aspects. This is consistent with transactional perspectives on occupation.

Furthermore, Heller's theory encourages the examination of the mundane and often overlooked aspects of daily life, which are fundamental to fully comprehending human occupation. This approach can uncover the complexities and meanings of everyday occupations, thereby expanding the scope of occupational science to include a broader range of human experiences.

Heller's emphasis on everyday life aligns well with critical perspectives in occupational science that seek to deconstruct hegemonic and neoliberal influences in the field. This alignment can foster interdisciplinary dialogues and collaborations, enriching both theoretical and practical knowledge within the discipline.

Finally, the conceptual framework Heller's perspective provides offers valuable insights for occupational therapy practice. It aligns with an emancipatory vision aimed at expanding citizenship and fostering greater social participation among individuals.

In conclusion, recognizing the significance of everyday occupations allows to promote to individuals to assert control over their existence, interpret their reality in a nuanced manner, and emphasize their unique identity, even amidst daily challenges. This holistic

understanding underscores the dynamic interaction between individuals and their environment, highlighting their capacity to shape their identity through ongoing interaction with the world around them. What constitutes a contribution for both occupational therapy and for the complexity of research in occupational science.

Positionality of Authors

We consider it important to highlight the perspective from which we write these reflections. Therefore, we explicitly state our positionalities: the first author identifies as a white, Latin American, cisgender, and gay man, while the second author identifies as a Black, Latin American, queer, and cisgender man. We believe that our particularities allow us to perceive reality from non-hegemonic positions, enabling us to engage with alterity within the academic context. This perspective is informed by critical theories and pragmatist viewpoints drawn from our Latin American experiences, which guide our interpretation and analysis.

7. References

- Absolom, S., & Roberts, A. (2011). Connecting with Others: The Meaning of Social Eating as an Everyday Occupation for Young People. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 18(4), 339-346. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2011.586324>
- Abumusse, L. V. d. M. (2016). *Transtorno de ansiedade social e os prejuízos funcionais relacionados a vida cotidiana: validação de escalas*. [PhD Dissertation] Universidade de São Paulo. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.11606/T.59.2009.tde-07052009-134731>
- Adrian, A. (2013). An Exploration of Lutheran Music-Making among US Immigrant and Refugee Populations. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 20(2), 160-172. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2013.775690>
- Aguilar, A., Boerema, C., & Harrison, J. (2010). Meanings attributed by older adults to computer use. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 17(1), 27-33. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2010.9686669>
- Albornoz, F. M. S., Tripailaf, J. A. R., Provost, M. F. C., Huerta, C. T. L., Rocha, A. N. G., & Cirineu, C. T. (2023). Daily life of informal caregivers: perspectives from occupational therapy. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 31, e3440. <https://doi.org/10.1590/2526-8910.ctoAO263434402>
- Aldrich, R. (2008). From complexity theory to transactionalism: Moving occupational science forward in theorizing the complexities of behavior. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 15(3), 147-156. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2008.9686624>

- Arola, L. A., Dellenborg, L., & Häggblom-Kronlöf, G. (2018). Occupational perspective of health among persons ageing in the context of migration. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 25(1), 65-75. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2017.1368411>
- Bauman, Z. (2013). *The individualized society*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Bezerra, W. C., Lopes, R. E., & Basso, A. C. d. S. (2022). The structures of everyday life and occupational therapy: tensioning limits and possibilities in/of the professional practice. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 30, e3031. <https://doi.org/10.1590/2526-8910.ctoEN22983031>
- Bundgaard, K. M. (2005). The Meaning of Everyday Meals in Living Units for Older People. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 12(2), 91-101. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2005.9686552>
- Cazeiro, A. P. M., Felix Barcellos, V., Fernandes, R. D., Costa, M. C. d., Takeiti, B. A., & Correia, R. L. (2022). Conceitos de atividade, ocupação e cotidiano: um estudo exploratório com graduandos de terapia ocupacional. *Revista Chilena de Terapia Ocupacional*, 23(2), 125-139. <https://doi.org/10.5354/0719-5346.2022.64146>
- Cerón, N. P., & Morrison, R. (2019). Patriarcado, masculinidad hegemónica y ocupaciones: procesos de perpetuación del sexismo. *Revista Argentina de Terapia Ocupacional*, 5(1), 75-84. <https://revista.terapia-ocupacional.org.ar/RATO/2019jul-ens.pdf>
- Cerón, N. P., & Morrison, R. (2024). Occupation as a gender reproducer: an approach to hegemonic masculinity. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 32. <https://doi.org/10.1590/2526-8910.ctoAO279936442>
- Christiansen, C., & Townsend, E. A. (2009). *Introduction to occupation: The art of science and living*.
- Cruz, D. M. C. d., Rodrigues, D. d. S., & Carey, H. (2021). Philosophical Influences on Occupational Therapy in Brazil. A Historical Timeline. In S. D. Taff (Ed.), *Philosophy and Occupational Therapy. Informing Education, Research, and Practice* (pp. 189-199). SLACK Incorporated.
- Cutchin, M., & Dickie, V. (2012). Transactionalism: Occupational science and the pragmatic attitude. In G. Whiteford & C. Hocking (Eds.), *Occupational Science: Society, Inclusion, Participation*. Wiley-Blackwell. <Go to WoS>://WOS:000221527900009
- Cutchin, M., & Dickie, V. (2013). *Transactional perspectives on occupation*. Springer.
- Domínguez, M. M., Rivas-Quarneti, N., & Gonzalo, N. G. (2018). “I gave birth to him and he gave me my life”: study of occupational transition linked to motherhood of two women with mental disorders. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 26, 271-285. <https://doi.org/10.4322/2526-8910.ctoAO1156>
- Duarte Cuervo, C. (2023). Conflicto armado, paz y terapia ocupacional en Colombia: recorridos y desafíos. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 31. <https://doi.org/10.1590/2526-8910.ctoAO273435143>
- Durocher, E., Gibson, B. E., & Rappolt, S. (2014). Occupational Justice: A Conceptual Review. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 21(4), 418-430. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2013.775692>
- Farias, L., & Asaba, E. (2013). “The Family Knot”: Negotiating Identities and Cultural Values through the Everyday Occupations of an Immigrant Family in Sweden. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 20(1), 36-47. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2013.764580>
- Farias, L., Rudman, D., & Magalhaes, L. (2016). Illustrating the Importance of Critical Epistemology to Realize the Promise of Occupational Justice. *Otjr-Occupation*

- Participation and Health*, 36(4), 234-243.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/1539449216665561>
- Fritz, H., & Cutchin, M. (2017). The transactional perspective on occupation: A way to transcend the individual in health promotion interventions and research. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 24(4), 446-457.
- Galheigo, S. M. (2020). Occupational therapy, everyday life and the fabric of life: theoretical-conceptual contributions for the construction of critical and emancipatory perspectives. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 28, 5-25.
<https://doi.org/10.4322/2526-8910.ctoAO2590>
- Galvaan, R. (2021). Generative disruption through occupational science: Enacting possibilities for deep human connection. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 28(1), 6-18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2020.1818276>
- Galvaan, R., Peters, L., Richards, L. A., Francke, M., & Krenzer, M. (2022). Pedagogies within occupational therapy curriculum: centering a decolonial praxis in community development practice. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 30.
- Giddens, A., & Sutton, P. W. (2021). *Sociology* (9th ed.). Polity.
- Gonçalves, M. V., & Malfitano, A. P. S. (2020). Brazilian youth experiencing poverty: Everyday life in the favela. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 27(3), 311-326.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2020.1757495>
- Guajardo, A. (2012). Enfoque y praxis en Terapia Ocupacional. Reflexiones desde una perspectiva de la Terapia Ocupacional crítica. *Revista Terapia Ocupacional Galicia*, 9(5), 18-29.
- Guajardo, A., & Malfitano, A. P. S. (2023). Apuntes críticos a los fundamentos de la terapia ocupacional: apertura para una posible Terapia Ocupacional Otra. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 31. <https://doi.org/10.1590/2526-8910.ctoARF267634913>
- Gutiérrez, P. (2011). *Terapia Ocupacional, una disciplina para la autonomía. Prácticas y discursos de gubernamentalidad y subjetivación en torno a una ciencia emergente [Tesis. Doctorado en Psicología Social]*. Universidad Autónoma de Barcelona.
- Hammell, K. W. (2011). Resisting Theoretical Imperialism in the Disciplines of Occupational Science and Occupational Therapy. *British Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 74(1), 27-33. <https://doi.org/10.4276/030802211X12947686093602>
- Hasselkus, B. R. (2006). The World of Everyday Occupation: Real People, Real Lives. *The American Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 60(6), 627-640.
<https://doi.org/10.5014/ajot.60.6.627>
- Heidegger, M. (2008). *El concepto de tiempo (tratado de 1924)*. Herder Editorial.
- Heidegger, M. (2014). *Problemas fundamentales de la fenomenología (1919-1920)*. Alianza Editorial.
- Heller, A. (1978). *The Theory of Need in Marx*. Humanities Press.
- Heller, A. (2002). *Sociología de la vida cotidiana*. Barcelona: Ed. Península.
- Heller, A. (2008). *O cotidiano e a história*. Paz e Terra.
- Junior, H. P. C., de Almeida, S. C., & de França Drummond, A. (2024). Occupations of users of a Brazilian mental health service during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 31(1), 149-162.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2024.2311352>

- Junior, J. D. L., Rudman, D. L., & Lopes, R. E. Alliances between social occupational therapy and critical occupational science: Propositions to mobilize social justice. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 1-17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2024.2374308>
- Krishnagiri, S., & Adler, K. (2022). Occupations, social connections, health, and well-being of US university students during COVID-19. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 29(3), 306-322. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2022.2100457>
- Krishnakumaran, T., Bhatt, M., Kiriazis, K., & Giddings, C. E. (2022). Exploring the Role of Occupational Therapy and Forced Migration in Canada. *Canadian Journal of Occupational Therapy*, 89(3), 238-248. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00084174221084463>
- Kuo, A. (2018). A Transactional View: Occupation as a Means to Create Experiences that Matter. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 18(2), 131-138. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2011.575759>
- Lapierre, M., & Samacá, J. (2024). Terapia ocupacional sociopolítica: reflexiones conceptuales y prácticas. *Terapia Ocupacional Galicia*(21), 62-70. <https://doi.org/S1885-527X202400010011>
- Lavalley, R. (2017). Developing the transactional perspective of occupation for communities: "How well are we doing together?". *Journal of Occupational Science*, 24(4), 458-469. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2017.1367321>
- Leão, A., & Barros, S. (2012). Território e serviço comunitário de saúde mental: as concepções presentes nos discursos dos atores do processo da reforma psiquiátrica. *Saúde e Sociedade*, 21(3), 572-586. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1590/S0104-12902012000300005>
- Leite, J. D. J. (2024). "A gente tá falando de deixar viver uma galera que morre": práticas profissionais de terapeutas ocupacionais junto à população dissidente de gêneros e sexualidades no cenário brasileiro / "We are talking about letting live a group of people who are dying": Professional practices of occupational therapists working with gender and sexuality dissidents in the Brazilian context. [PhD Occupational Therapy] University of Sao Carlos, Brazil.
- Lopes, R. E., & Malfitano, A. P. S. (Eds.). (2016). *Terapia Ocupacional Social. Desenhos teóricos e contornos práticos*. EdUFSCar.
- Malfitano, A. P. S. (2022). An anthropophagic proposition in occupational therapy knowledge: Driving our actions towards social life. *World Federation of Occupational Therapists Bulletin*, 78(2), 70-82. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14473828.2022.2135065>
- Malfitano, A. P. S., Borba, P. L. d. O., & Lopes, R. E. (2023). Palabras, conceptos y contextos históricos y culturales: la pluralidad en Terapia Ocupacional. *Revista Ocupación Humana*, 23(2), 104-135. <https://doi.org/10.25214/25907816.1591>
- Marcolino, T. Q. (2016). Como trabalhamos com a noção de ampliação de cotidiano: considerações a partir do Método de Terapia Ocupacional Dinâmica. In T. S. Matsukura & M. M. Salles (Eds.), *Cotidiano, atividade humana e ocupação: perspectivas da terapia ocupacional no campo da saúde mental* (pp. 105-122). EdUFSCar.
- Marx, K. (1844). *Economic and Philosophic Manuscripts of 1844*. Editora.
- Maximino, V. S., & Tedesco, S. (2016). Rotina, hábitos, cotidiano: no banal e no sutil, a trama da vida. In T. S. Matsukura & M. M. Salles (Eds.), *Cotidiano, atividade humana e ocupação: perspectivas da terapia ocupacional no campo da saúde mental* (pp. 123-146). EdUFSCar.

- Miller, D. (2008). *The comfort of things*. Polity.
- Monclus, P. G., & Tarrès, J. P. (2016). Occupational Therapy: Autonomy, Governmentality and Subjectification. *Revista de Estudios Sociales*, 1(57), 68-77. <https://doi.org/10.7440/res57.2016.05>
- Morrison, R., & Poblete-Almendras, M. J. (2023). Discourses on Sexuality and Occupations: Reflections for Occupational Therapy and Occupational Science. *Sexes*, 4(3), 392-401. <https://doi.org/10.3390/sexes4030025>
- Morrison, R., Araya-Hernández, C., Arrué-Jara, V., & Céspedes-Olivares, D. (2023). LGBT people and Occupational Science: a literature review. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 31, e3506. <https://doi.org/10.1590/2526-8910.ctoAR268535062>
- Morrison, R., Guajardo, A., & Schliebener, M. (2016). Debates y reflexiones para una Ciencia de la Ocupación crítica y social. Diálogos para comprender la Ocupación Humana. *Revista Argentina de Terapia Ocupacional*, 2(1), 40-58.
- Morrison, R., Olivares, D., & Vidal, D. (2011). La filosofía de la Ocupación Humana y el Paradigma Social de la Ocupación. Algunas reflexiones y propuestas sobre epistemologías actuales en Terapia Ocupacional y Ciencias de la Ocupación [The Philosophy of Human Occupation and the Social Paradigm of the Occupation. Some reflections and suggestions on current epistemologies in Occupational Therapy and Occupational Science]. *Revista Chilena de Terapia Ocupacional*, 11(2), 102-119. <https://doi.org/10.5354/0717-5346.2011.17785>
- Morrison, R., Silva, C. R., Correia, R. L., & Wertheimer, L. (2021). Why an Occupational Science in Latin America? Possible relationships with Occupational Therapy from a pragmatist perspective. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 29, e2081. <https://doi.org/10.1590/2526-8910.ctoEN2081>
- Nizzero, A., Cote, P., & Cramm, H. (2017). Occupational disruption: A scoping review. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 24(2), 114-127. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2017.1306791>
- Parente, M., Tofani, M., De Santis, R., Esposito, G., Santilli, V., & Galeoto, G. (2017). The Role of the Occupational Therapist in Disaster Areas: Systematic Review. *Occupational Therapy International*, 2017(1), 6474761. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/6474761>
- Parkin, R. A., & Johnson, K. R. Interrogating whiteness: Critical reflections on occupational science scholarship and social responsibility. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2024.2312996>
- Raanaas, R. K., Aase, S. Ø., & Huot, S. (2019). Finding meaningful occupation in refugees' resettlement: A study of amateur choir singing in Norway. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 26(1), 65-76. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2018.1537884>
- Rudman, D. (2013). Enacting the critical potential of occupational science: Problematizing the 'individualizing of occupation'. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 20(4), 298-313.
- Rudman, D. (2014). Embracing and enacting an 'occupational imagination': Occupational science as transformative. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 21(4), 373-388.
- Salar, S., Pekçetin, S., Günal, A., & Akel, B. S. (2022). Time-use, occupational balance, and temporal life satisfaction of university students in Turkey during isolation period of COVID-19. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 29(3), 284-294. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2022.2031260>

- Salles, M. M. (2011). *Vida cotidiana de usuários de CAPS: a (in)visibilidade no território*. (PhD Dissertation). Universidade de São Paulo.
- Salles, M. M., & Matsukura, T. S. (2013). Estudo de revisão sistemática sobre o uso do conceito de cotidiano no campo da terapia ocupacional no Brasil/Systematic review study on the use of the concept of daily life in the field of occupational therapy in Brazil. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 21(2). <https://doi.org/10.4322/cto.2013.028>
- Salles, M. M., & Matsukura, T. S. (2015). Estudo de revisão sistemática sobre o uso do conceito de cotidiano no campo da Terapia Ocupacional na literatura de língua inglesa/Systematic review about everyday life in Occupational Therapy English papers. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 23(1), 197-210. <https://doi.org/10.4322/0104-4931.ctoARL510>
- Schliebener, M. (2015). Los supuestos que subyacen a las principales teorías de Ann Wilcock y la necesidad de la pregunta ontológica por la ocupación humana. *Revista Terapia Ocupacional Galicia*, 12(21), 20 p. <Go to WoS>://WOS:000290570500003
- Schliebener, M. (2018). El diálogo entre terapia ocupacional y filosofía en torno al problema del existir desde el pensamiento de Heidegger. *Cinta de Moebio*(62), 246-260. <https://doi.org/10.4067/S0717-554X2018000200246>
- Schliebener, M. (2020). La ocupación como objeto y herramienta: ¿cuándo la ocupación está viva? *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 28, 1051-1060. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.4322/2526-8910.ctoARF2043>
- Schliebener, M. (2021). Terapia ocupacional y modelo biopsicosocial: tensiones desde una comprensión existencial de ser humano ocupacional. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 29. <https://doi.org/10.1590/2526-8910.ctoARF2059>
- Sima, L., Thomas, Y., & Lowrie, D. (2017). Occupational disruption and natural disaster: Finding a 'new normal' in a changed context. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 24(2), 128-139. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2017.1306790>
- Simaan, J. (2020). Decolonising occupational science education through learning activities based on a study from the Global South. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 27(3), 432-442.
- Simó, S., Guajardo, A., Corrêa, F., Galheigo, S., & García-Ruiz, S. (Eds.). (2016). *Terapias Ocupacionales desde el Sur. Derechos humanos, ciudadanía y participación*. Editorial USACH.
- Suleman, A., & Whiteford, G. E. (2013). Understanding Occupational Transitions in Forced Migration: The Importance of Life Skills in Early Refugee Resettlement. *Journal of Occupational Science*, 20(2), 201-210. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14427591.2012.755908>
- Taff, S. D., & Putnam, L. (2022). Northern philosophies and professional neocolonialism in occupational therapy: a historical review and critique. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 30.
- Turcotte, P.-L., & Holmes, D. (2021). The (dis)obedient occupational therapist: A reflection on dissent against disciplinary propaganda. *Cadernos Brasileiros de Terapia Ocupacional*, 29.
- Yañez, R., & Pizarro, E. (2015). El ser y el tiempo. Una posibilidad ontológica para la terapia ocupacional. *Revista Chilena de Terapia Ocupacional*, 14(2), 267-276. <https://doi.org/DOI: 10.5354/0717-5346.2014.35728>